

score

D3.12-User Documentation for Testing Tools and Data

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning / Full text
EBA	Ecosystem-Based Approach
D	Deliverable
WP	Work Package
T	Task
CCLL	Coastal City Living Lab
GEE	Google Earth Engine
DSAS	Digital Shoreline Analysis System
api	Application Programming Interface
ROI	Region of Interest
SCE	Shoreline Change Envelope
WLR	Weighted Linear Regression
SLR	Sea Level Rise
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
WW3	WaveWatch 3
RCP	Representative Concentration Pathways
TMA	Texel-Marsen-Arsloe
ETA	Estimated Tidal Amplitude

BACKGROUND: ABOUT THE SCORE PROJECT

SCORE is a four-year EU-funded project aiming to increase climate resilience in European coastal cities.

The intensification of extreme weather events, coastal erosion and sea-level rise are major challenges to be urgently addressed by European coastal cities. The science behind these disruptive phenomena is complex, and advancing climate resilience requires progress in data acquisition, forecasting, and understanding of the potential risks and impacts for real-scenario interventions. The Ecosystem-Based Approach (EBA) supported by smart technologies has potential to increase climate resilience of European coastal cities; however, it is not yet adequately understood and coordinated at European level.

SCORE outlines a co-creation strategy, developed via a network of 10 Coastal City 'Living Labs' (CCLs), to rapidly, equitably and sustainably enhance coastal city climate resilience through EBAs and sophisticated digital technologies.

The 10 Coastal City Living Labs involved in the project are: Sligo and Dublin, Ireland; Barcelona/Vilanova i la Geltrú, Benidorm and Basque Country, Spain; Oeiras, Portugal; Massa, Italy; Piran, Slovenia; Gdansk, Poland; Samsun, Turkey.

SCORE will establish an integrated coastal zone management framework for strengthening EBA and smart coastal city policies, creating European leadership in coastal city climate change adaptation in line with The Paris Agreement. It will provide innovative platforms to empower stakeholders' deployment of EBAs to increase climate resilience, business opportunities and financial sustainability of coastal cities.

The SCORE interdisciplinary team consists of 28 world-leading organisations from academia, local authorities, RPOs, and SMEs encompassing a wide range of skills including environmental science and policy, climate modelling, citizen and social science, data management, coastal management and engineering, security and technological aspects of smart sensing research.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is a deliverable of the SCORE project, funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003534.

The Deliverable 3.12, entitled "User Documentation for Testing Tools and Data", is the twelfth report of Work Package 3 "Regional and Local Projections, Analyses, Modelling and Uncertainties", corresponding to Task 3.6 "Testing". The aim of this report is to provide documentation for testing tools and data as a detailed and essential guide for the effective application, validation, and operational use of the models and tools developed in WP3 tasks.

This technical document is primarily designed to assist researchers, technical staff, and stakeholders from CCLLs, in validating the developed frameworks, tools and models tailored for flood hazard assessment, extreme event modelling, and long-term coastal dynamics. Additionally, it focuses on testing the applicability and reliability of developed tools in the context of various coastal settings within the CCLLs.

LINKS WITH OTHER PROJECT ACTIVITIES

The testing tools are specifically designed to validate the methodologies and models developed in earlier WP3 tasks, including T 3.4 "Short term hazard modelling", and T 3.5 "Modelling of the long-term evolution of the coastline". Also, T 8.5 "Assessment of integrated early warning support and spatial digital twin" from WP 8 "Development of integrated early warning support and spatial digital twin solution prototypes".

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1. INTRODUCTION

Coastal cities are at the frontline of climate change impacts, facing a growing array of challenges that threaten their infrastructure, ecosystems, and communities. Rising sea levels, intensifying storm events, coastal erosion, and urban flooding are no longer future scenarios; they are current realities that demand urgent, data-driven solutions. These multifaceted challenges require innovative approaches to prediction, planning, and mitigation, enabling urban areas to adapt to changing conditions while safeguarding lives, property, and livelihoods.

The user documentation for testing tools and data serves as a detailed and essential guide for the effective application, validation, and operational use of the models and tools developed in WP3 tasks including T3.4 "Short term hazard modelling", and T3.5 "Modelling of the long-term evolution of the coastline".. This document is primarily designed to assist technical staff, stakeholders, and researchers from CCLs, in utilizing and validating the models and tools tailored for flood hazard assessment, extreme event modeling, and long-term coastal dynamics within urban coastal settings. This user documentation consolidates the developed findings, models, and tools as foundations to provide a final set of applicable, integrated tools, primarily aimed at testing and validating the models' ability to simulate real-world conditions and support decision-making processes for coastal risk management.

This document will guide users through the process of applying the testing tools and interpreting their results, with the ultimate goal of supporting effective decision-making for coastal risk management. By ensuring that these tools are rigorously tested, users can confidently utilize them to plan for and mitigate the risks posed by climate change, sea-level rise, storm surges, and other coastal hazards.

Through continuous validation, users will be able to fine-tune the tools, improve their performance, and apply them to specific local contexts, ensuring that the models are robust and applicable across a range of coastal environments. This documentation provides detailed instructions on how to deploy and test these models, interpret the outcomes, and integrate the findings into local climate action plans. The ability to effectively test and validate these models will ensure their real-world applicability and enhance their value in ongoing coastal management and policy development.

2. OVERVIEW OF THE TESTING TOOLS

The testing tools present in Task 3.6 are integral to the validation and refinement of the models developed throughout WP3, which focuses on regional and local projections, modeling, and uncertainty analysis for coastal urban environments. These tools are designed to test the ability of the models to replicate real-world conditions and are essential for ensuring the accuracy and reliability of the predictions made by these models.

The tools developed for this task focus on several key areas essential for coastal hazard assessment, including flood hazard predictions, extreme climate event modelling, coastal erosion, and urban resilience. These tools allow for the validation of models that simulate the effects of sea-level rise, storm surge events, and extreme weather conditions under various climate scenarios. The testing tools are specifically designed to validate the models produced earlier in the WP3 tasks, using real-world data and earth observations that allow users to explore various hazard scenarios, quantify the potential impacts of extreme events, and assess long-term coastal evolution. By applying these tools, users can evaluate the efficacy of the models in forecasting flood events, and coastal changes at urban scales.

Key areas that the developed tools address include:

- **Coastal Erosion and Shoreline Change:** Using long-term coastal evolution models to validate the impacts of coastal erosion, sediment transport, and shoreline change over time, assessing their potential effects on urban coastal areas and their resilience to sea level rise. This analysis can be found in detail in the historical and current shoreline dynamics analysis, as well as in the future shoreline evolution modelling packages.
- **Flood Hazard Prediction:** Validation of flood model using real-world data, to simulate urban flooding scenarios and assess floodplain risks. This analysis can be found in detail in the flood extent validation, as well as in the flood extent in climatological scenarios packages.

3. DEVELOPED TOOLS AND APPLICATIONS

The developed packages focus on the power of advanced remote sensing technologies based on shoreline observations to quantify the coastline dynamics, including coastal evolution, erosion and accretion patterns, flood extent, flood mapping, and flooding dynamics. By integrating earth observation data with spatial analysis through different coding platforms and libraries, these approaches enable the assessment of coastline stability and movement of coastline over time, detecting long-term dynamic changes, development of flood extent maps, and analysis of complex flooding dynamics. The combination of these approaches with advanced statistical techniques, and climate modelling and scenarios can help in forecasting future coastal dynamics.

3.1 Historical And Current Shoreline Dynamics Analysis Package

[Google Earth Engine \(GEE\)](#): Used for retrieving and processing satellite imagery (e.g., Landsat, Sentinel-2) to derive historical shoreline positions, detect changes over time and integrate with Digital Shoreline Analysis System (DSAS) for quantifying coastal dynamics and analysing erosion rates. This framework allows for detailed assessments of shoreline changes over time. With GEE, you can access a wide range of functions specifically developed for computing in Earth Engine, and apply them across multiple images simultaneously, all powered by Google's computational infrastructure. This means you no longer need to download and analyze individual tiles one by one or worry about your local storage. For a helpful tutorial on using GEE, you can refer to [About Google Earth Engine](#), or [Introductory course to Google Earth Engine](#).

Satellite imagery is retrieved via Google Earth Engine's platform, including Landsat (5, 7, 8, and 9) with a spatial resolution of 30 meters, and Sentinel-2 imagery with 10 meter spatial resolution. These images are obtained across multiple spectral bands, enabling detailed analysis and classification of coastal features and processes.

[Image Processing](#): The images are processed to enhance clarity and remove cloud interference, ensuring accurate coastline detection without restrictions. This step helps to improve the quality of shoreline delineation.

[Water/Land Classification](#): Advanced algorithms classify the imagery into water, land, and transitional zones. This classification enhances the accuracy of shoreline delineation and change detection. Additionally, an advanced tool has been developed to automate shoreline detection and vectorization, streamlining the analysis process.

Coastline dynamics and patterns analysis: Shoreline positions extracted from water/land classified imagery are analysed using DSAS. This tool calculates the movements and rates of shoreline change, identifies areas of significant erosion or accretion, and generates trend lines to visualize long-term coastal dynamics. Statistical methods are applied to validate shoreline movement measurements, assess the significance of trends, and quantify uncertainties in erosion rates over time. Additionally, DSAS offers the possibility of predicting future shoreline trends based on the regression behaviour of long-term shoreline movements.

Accessibility of Tools

[Coastsat \(Python toolkit\)](#), Google Earth Engine (Java, and Python application programming interface (api)), and [DSAS](#) are open-access platforms and tools, freely available to users and researchers. These tools are integrated and complementary to each other, especially in long-term analysis. Coastsat and GEE are used to quantify the historical shoreline curvatures and dynamics, while DSAS is used afterward to spatially and statistically analyze for the shoreline dynamics movement, patterns and trends.

1. Coastsat is an open source Python toolkit designed to enable users to extract and analyse time series of shoreline positions for any coastline worldwide using publicly available satellite imagery, such as Landsat and Sentinel-2. The toolkit integrates with GEE to facilitate the retrieval, processing, and analysis of satellite data.

To use Coastsat, users must have an account on Google Earth Engine, which allows access to and retrieval of the satellite image. Users should define their region of interest (ROI) as a polygon coordinate or integrate it as a GeoJSON file. One key step involves digitizing the general curvature of the shoreline to train the model on the area's specific shoreline geometry. This step can be challenging, especially due to limitations in the resolution of satellite imagery, which may affect the model's ability to accurately detect intricate shoreline features.

Once processed, the extracted shoreline positions are exported as GeoJSON files, enabling seamless integration with other spatial analysis tools and applications for further evaluation and decision-making.

2. The integration of GEE with the DSAS begins with the use of JavaScript for the retrieval, processing, and analysis of composite satellite imagery, such as Landsat and Sentinel-2, available on the GEE platform. Users can define their ROI interactively using the platform's mapping interface.

An automated shoreline detection algorithm is employed to extract and vectorize shorelines within the study area. This process significantly streamlines the analysis by generating accurate shoreline geometries, which are then exported as GeoJSON files. These files can be seamlessly integrated with DSAS for further analysis.

Within DSAS, the extracted shorelines are used to quantify transect-based measurements of coastal dynamics, such as erosion and accretion rates. This integration allows for a detailed assessment of coastline movement, providing critical insights into shoreline changes and trends over time.

This framework was applied and tested to analyse the dynamics of Dublin's shoreline using automated processing tools for Earth observation data. The dynamics of Dublin's coastline were analysed over a 12 km stretch, from Dún Laoghaire Harbour to Northern Dublin Bay, based on satellite observations covering from 1985 to 2023. The GEE platform was used to retrieve, access, process, and analyse optical satellite imagery from Landsat (5, 7, 8, and 9) and Sentinel-2.

The integration of the generated shoreline from GEE with the DSAS for spatial analysis is illustrated in Figure 1. This figure highlights the spatial distribution of shoreline movement along the Dublin coastline.

Figure 1 Dublin shoreline movement

The spatial analysis for the Dublin shoreline for long-term movement from 1985 to 2023 reflects the dynamic nature of the coastline as shown in Figure 1. This Figure represents the active and changeable coastline positions based on the Shoreline Change Envelope (SCE). The SCE refers to the shoreline movement in meters calculated as the absolute difference distance between the farthest seaward and the most landward shoreline positions along each transect. The SCE visualization identifies the most variability and instability of the shoreline as it shows in the Figure the blue and pink shoreline.

The transect analysis highlights varying degrees of coastal dynamics across the region. The central section of the study area exhibits the most significant shoreline changes, represented predominantly by pink and blue indicators. In contrast, the northern and southern sections, represented by yellow and orange colors, indicate moderate to minor shoreline movement.

The DSAS analysis for quantifying erosion rates is presented in Figure 2, which illustrates the annual shoreline change rates derived using the weighted linear regression (WLR) method for long-term coastline analysis. The WLR approach provides a robust statistical framework for long-term assessing shoreline dynamics, enabling the identification of both erosion and accretion trends.

Figure 2 Dublin shoreline yearly changing rate

The transect analysis based on WLR provides a clear distinction between erosional and accretional shoreline trends. Shorelines with a WLR value less than 0 ($WLR < 0$) indicate erosion, reflecting a net loss of land over time. However, shorelines with a WLR value greater than 0 ($WLR > 0$) signify accretion, representing a net gain of land. Based on this classification, Figure 3 illustrates the visualization of the erosional and accretional shorelines, highlighting the varying rates of shoreline change across the coastal area.

Figure 3 Dublin coastline trends

Figure 4 demonstrates the transect analysis of the Dublin coastline, showcasing the patterns of erosional and accretional shorelines. The figure visually represents the distribution of erosion and accretion along transects of the coastline.

Total Transects	603
Total Erosional Transects	378
Total Accretional Transects	153
Total Stable Transects	5
Erosional Shoreline Length	7.5 Km
Erosional Transects (%)	63%
Accretional Shoreline Length	3 Km
Accretional Transects (%)	26%
Stable Transects (%)	1%
Mean shoreline change	-1.30901
Max shoreline change	5.16
Min shoreline change	-7.74
Mean Erosion	-1.48973
Std. Erosion	2.810638
Mean Accretion	0.326169
Std. Accretion	0.945741

Figure 4 Dublin coastline pattern

As shown in Figure 4, the historical analysis of the Dublin coastline reveals that 63% of the transects are classified as erosional shorelines, while 26% are classified as accretional shorelines. This analysis highlights that the majority of the coastal area is experiencing erosion, emphasizing the need for focused intervention and management strategies to address the ongoing coastal degradation in the region.

In conclusion, the automated coastline detection method was implemented to improve mapping efficiency and enhance shoreline detection accuracy, providing detailed insights into coastal changes such as erosion and accretion. By integrating the DSAS, the approach enabled long-term shoreline analysis, allowing for the quantification of erosion rates and the identification of trends. The results revealed that 63% of the examined transects exhibited erosional trends, indicating that the studied section of Dublin's shoreline is predominantly erosional.

3.2 Future Shoreline Evolution Modelling Package

Various models are used to understand, predict, and manage coastal evolution, focusing on long-term shoreline changes influenced by natural processes and human activities, combining the strengths of different models to address varying temporal scales.

The COSMOS-COAST model is a highly adaptable tool for simulating long-term, climate-scale shoreline changes over decades to centuries. Leveraging satellite-derived shoreline observations, historical surveys, and marine data such as wave dynamics and sea-level trends, this one-line model integrates data using a Kalman filter for efficient parameter estimation and calibration. Its implicit numerical method enhances computational efficiency, while the assimilation of historical and observed trends minimizes the need for complex calibrations.

The COSMOS-COAST model is capable of projecting future shoreline positions under various scenarios, designing for climate scale simulations for climate projection with sea-level rise (SLR). It provides georeferenced outputs that include shoreline projections with uncertainty estimates, sediment transport calculations, and visualizations compatible with various platforms.

For modelling short-term coastal changes, particularly those caused by extreme events like storms, the XBeach model is used. This process-based, two-dimensional model simulates wave dynamics, sediment transport, and morphological changes during storm events. It captures the complex interactions between waves, currents, and sediment, offering detailed predictions for storm-induced changes. However, XBeach has limitations, such as its

inability to represent post-storm adjustments and its high computational resource requirements. These constraints make it less suitable for long-term evolution studies.

To address these challenges, a hybrid approach is often employed, combining XBeach's short-term predictions with the COSMOS-Coast model's long-term projections. While XBeach excels in providing short-term, detailed predictions, it struggles with representing certain long-term processes. By integrating the results from both models, this hybrid approach offers a more comprehensive understanding of coastal change, bridging the gap between storm-induced short-term dynamics, long-term shoreline evolution, and balance between computational efficiency and accuracy.

The models are applied to specific case studies, such as Benidorm (Spain) and Massa (Italy), to demonstrate their practical application and address site-specific challenges. In Benidorm, the models assess the impact of climate change and SLR on two distinct beaches, considering local wave conditions and coastal structures. In Massa, the models address a more complex scenario with limited sediment supply, existing coastal defences, and vulnerability to flooding. These case studies highlight the importance of considering local factors, such as wave climate, coastal morphology, and human interventions, in coastal evolution modelling.

Accessibility of Tool

[COSMOS-COAST](https://doi.org/10.5066/P95T9188) model: Vitousek, S., 2023, CoSMoS-COAST: The Coastal, One-line, Assimilated, Simulation Tool of the Coastal Storm Modeling System: U.S. Geological Survey software release, <https://doi.org/10.5066/P95T9188>

Model Scripts and Packages Required:

- MATLAB Version: 9.13 (other versions with potential modifications).
- Toolboxes: Control System, Signal Processing, Mapping, Image Processing, Statistics and Machine Learning, Text Analytics.

Scripts Downloaded Folders:

- 'model': Contains main model code (CoSMoS_COAST_California_scalable.m), routines for model tuning, and output saving.
- 'transects': Model transect data (transects.mat) and related code for data derivation.
- 'waves': Wave forcing data (waves.mat) and code for data derivation (critical inputs for simulations).
- 'shorelines': Historical shoreline observations (shorelines.mat) and code to generate these data.
- 'matlab_helper_functions': Subroutines and toolboxes for model functionality (e.g., output files).
- Data Requirements: Input data must be adapted to the model and study area specifics. Scripts for this adaptation are provided in a separate folder, ensuring consistency and accuracy.

Available Output Scripts:

- plot_CoSMoS_COAST_results.m: Plots instantaneous simulation results for a specified transect.
- save_CoSMoS_COAST_figures.m: Saves figures of simulation results, linked to .kml for visualization.
- save_CoSMoS_COAST_figures_parallel.m: Parallel version of the above script (requires Parallel Computing Toolbox).
- save_CoSMoS_COAST_skill_metrics.m: Compares model results to observations, reporting skill metrics.
- save_CoSMoS_COAST_output.m: Periodically saves output variables at specified intervals.
- save_CoSMoS_COAST_results_FINAL.m: Writes final simulation results to .kml, .xlsx, and .mat files, integrating additional metadata.

3.3 Flood Extent Validation Package

The outputs of the model, representing flood extent, are validated through a pixel-by-pixel comparison between reference maps and the flood maps generated by the model for the historical flood events. To generate reference maps, a method leveraging Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) images, provided by COSMO-SkyMed and Sentinel-1 missions, has been exploited to detect flooded areas in the CCLLs area. The procedure is based on the unique radar signature of water, defined by the backscattering coefficient (σ_0). The methodology, built on the approach proposed by [1], is composed of an ISODATA classification and a fuzzy logic approach. It has been applied separately to rural and urban areas. Change detection is incorporated when the configuration of pre-flood images aligns with the flood images. The image processing is carried out using ENVI, QGIS, and custom-written scripts. The validation coefficients are computed to assess the spatial agreement between the model outputs and maps obtained from the SAR image. To date, this procedure has been applied to the events in Marina di Massa (Italy) in November 2023, and in Vilanova i la Geltrú in August 2019, January 2020, and March and September 2024. Documentation of these events, along with records of the damaged areas provided by the CCLLs were used as support information for generating the flood extent maps.

3.4 Flood Extent In Climatological Scenarios: Model Validation

Following the technical descriptions of the XBeach [2] and FUNWAVE-TVD [7] models provided by D3.11, this section outlines the application of these tools to the Massa domain, highlighting the technical setups and simulation outcomes. These examples showcase the models' capacity to replicate complex flooding dynamics, aligning with the objectives of the SCORE project.

XBeach: Technical Setup and Results for the Massa site

XBeach was applied to the Massa domain to simulate the intricate dynamics of wave-induced flooding and its interactions with riverine processes. The modeling approach leveraged a 2D rectangular grid created from LIDAR and bathymetric surveys, ensuring precise representation of the coastal and fluvial terrain with a spatial resolution of 2 meters.

Figure 5 Massa 2D domain and bathymetry used for XBeach simulation created with the Python Toolbox

Figure 6 Massa 3D domain and bathymetry used for XBeach simulation created with the Python Toolbox

Table 1. Input files used to launch a simulation

	Name	Description
Files used to run the model	params.txt	Parameters input file
	modelname.dep	Bathymetry file
	modelname.grd	Grid file
	zs0file	Offshore water level
	disch_loc_file	Coordinate of the discharge points
	disch_timeseries_file	Timeseries of the discharge points
	bcfile	Offshore wave climate file

The non-hydrostatic mode of XBeach was selected to deliver detailed simulations of wave propagation, run-up, and overtopping processes. This choice was critical for accurately modeling the dynamic interactions between waves and coastal infrastructure, as well as the subsequent inland flooding. All such physical processes are relevant for a dissipative beach like the Massa case and better represent phenomena like the short wave run-up, otherwise computed in a parametric way. The offshore wave conditions were defined using a JONSWAP spectrum. This allowed the simulation to replicate significant storm events along the Massa coastline, with key parameters tailored for this application. These included a significant wave height of 4 meters, a peak wave period of 13 seconds, and an incident direction of 270°. To integrate sea-level variations, the simulation combined projections of sea-level rise, tidal range, and storm surge into a comprehensive water level input of 0.96 meters. Additionally, riverine influences were included through a constant discharge rate of 30 m³/s, representing the water flow from the Frigido river.

The simulation results provided a comprehensive understanding of flooding behavior across the Massa domain. The progression of wave-induced inundation highlighted areas at risk, particularly urban regions adjacent to the shoreline. The flooding extent evolved rapidly, with maximum inundation observed approximately one hour into the simulation. These findings underscored the vulnerability of the region to fast-escalating water levels during extreme weather events.

Figure 10 Water level temporal mean along a central transect

The simulation of one hour of a relatively severe constant wave action with no wind and no sediment transport. The river discharge is set to a constant value of $30 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, and the offshore water level is maintained at a constant value of 0.96 m . This value represents the combined effect of the predicted sea level rise in the RCP85 scenario for the period 2050-2100 (0.46 m), the maximum tide level for Massa (0.20 m), and an estimation of a severe storm surge event (0.30 m). Among the possible outputs, we focus on analyzing the water level, recorded in the output file every 30 seconds of simulation time. To analyze the NetCDF output, we develop two Python scripts: one for extracting PNG images and creating a video of the simulation, and another for estimating the mean water level along a specific transect. The figures presented include some extracted images, while another figure illustrates the mean water level along a central transect.

The analysis primarily focused on understanding flooding mechanisms, without simulating sediment transport. However, the potential for integrating this aspect exists, particularly by combining these models with long-term morphological projections from tools like COSMOS-COAST. This would allow for a more comprehensive assessment of erosion and deposition dynamics under changing climatic conditions.

Advanced postprocessing techniques were employed to analyze and visualize the simulation outputs. Time-lapse imagery captured the dynamic evolution of water levels, while transect analyses elucidated the spatial variations in flooding patterns. These tools not only facilitated a deeper understanding of the flooding mechanisms but also supported decision-making processes related to coastal resilience and infrastructure design.

Postprocessing scripts enabled the creation of time-lapse visualizations and transect analyses, aiding in the interpretation of wave dynamics and flooding impacts.

FUNWAVE-TVD: Technical Setup and Results for the Massa site

The FUNWAVE-TVD model, similar to XBeach, was also utilized to offer a comprehensive tool for model-to-model comparison and validation, specifically aimed at simulating phase-specific wave interactions. This includes a detailed representation of the dynamics of both riverine and coastal processes, with a particular focus on the complex interactions involved in combined riverine-coastal flooding scenarios within the Massa domain. The objective was to provide a robust framework for evaluating and comparing different modeling approaches in the context of coastal and combined flood hazard assessments.

The model utilizes a bathymetric grid specifically rotated and inverted to meet its input requirements. The ASCII grid format allowed precise representation of submerged and inland topographies, ensuring accurate data integration into the simulation.

Figure 11 Georeferenced Massa domain

Figure 12 Rotated and inverted Massa domain

The wave forcing was configured using a TMA spectrum to emulate offshore storm conditions. A significant wave height of 4 meters, a peak frequency of 0.0777 Hz, and a directional spreading parameter ($\gamma = 5$) were selected. These parameters were chosen to reflect intense wave activity, aligning with the study's aim of examining severe flooding scenarios. The tidal boundary conditions were adjusted to include an ETA of 1.54 meters, capturing the combined effects of riverine flow and tidal interactions.

For river discharge, a constant flow rate was implemented at the eastern boundary. The model employed a modified approach to ensure the presence of water from the initial time step, enabling the accurate simulation of hydrodynamic contributions from the Frigido river. Indeed, as there is no river module in FUNWAVE to implement the flow rate of a watercourse, alternative methods had to be employed, in particular through boundary conditions. Possible boundary conditions are: wall (mirror boundary condition used for a fully reflective wall), periodic (north-south boundary condition), and lateral frictional boundary condition which can be implemented by a sponge layer or a tide boundary. Simulating a river discharge was possible using the absorbing tidal boundary condition on the east side of the grid. In this module, the reference values (ETA, u , v) are tidal levels and tidal current velocities

specified either in input.txt or in a separate tide/surge file. For a constant tidal condition, values are constant and specified in input.txt, while for a time-varying tidal condition, the tidal level and velocity are specified in a file named in the input file, for example they can be specified in tide_data_west.txt, tide_data_east.txt, with the parameter TideBcType set as DATA type.

The problem with this module, which is not created to simulate river discharge, is that it needs to be implemented where there is already water. Otherwise, the model does not activate the tidal module in that boundary. In Massa domain, the inland area is very extended and riverbed elevation near the east boundary is about 1.5 m above sea level. For this reason, it was necessary to artificially lower some points at 0 m elevation at the east boundary in order to have water there even at the first time step. Then, we used HEC-RAS data from Task 3.4 coastal flood simulations to perform a constant flow rate of 15 m³/s in FUNWAVE. From the HEC-RAS simulations we extracted water depth information in that area which was added as ETA tide east boundary condition in the model. After a one-hour simulation, when the river and sea (with almost no waves at all) reached equilibrium, we extracted water level data along the river and compared it with those from HEC-RAS simulations. The graph in Fig. 13 shows that, although water level in FUNWAVE appears less uniform, the results are very similar, with a total mean difference of 0.04 m.

The simulations demonstrated detailed flooding dynamics driven by wave and river interactions. Wave-induced inundation patterns were particularly evident near the Frigido river mouth, where the interplay of fluvial discharge and coastal processes intensified the extent of flooding. The outputs highlighted the significance of accurately representing river-coast interactions to assess flood risks comprehensively.

Figure 13 Comparison of water level along Frigido river with FUNWAVE and HEC-RAS results

Comparisons with HEC-RAS results validated the consistency of FUNWAVE-TVD's predictions, with water level differences averaging only 0.04 meters. The higher spatial and temporal resolution of FUNWAVE-TVD provided an enriched understanding of localized flooding phenomena, surpassing the granularity of HEC-RAS.

Postprocessing was integral to interpreting the results. Consolidating outputs into NetCDF files facilitated advanced analysis, enabling the visualization of wave dynamics and flood extents over time. Transect analyses further illuminated the temporal mean water levels across key areas, enhancing the understanding of flooding patterns within the domain.

Waves run-up on the beach is observed, along with the sea advancing along the channel, which, in the final time steps, leads to water spilling into the urban area. Flood developing between $y = 2500-3000$ m is also observed.

Figure 14 Image extracted from the simulation at time t=1800 s

Figure 15 Image extracted from the simulation at time t=3600 s

Figure 16 Water level temporal mean along a central coastal transect

4. CONCLUSION

This deliverable outlines the development and application of advanced models and testing tools for coastal risk management, with a focus on predicting long-term shoreline changes, flood hazards, and the impacts of climate change on urban coastal areas. Through the integration of various models, we have demonstrated approaches that bridge the understanding, predict and manage coastal evolution. The tools developed, including those for coastal erosion, shoreline change, and flood hazard predictions, provide essential outputs for validating real-world conditions, refining model accuracy, and supporting effective decision-making in coastal management.

By ensuring rigorous testing and validation, these models offer reliable insights into future coastal dynamics, aiding in the formulation of climate adaptation strategies and sustainable management practices. The continuous application and refinement of these tools will help coastal cities mitigate the impacts of sea-level rise, storm surges, and other climate-related hazards, ensuring resilient and sustainable coastal environments for the future.

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